

CREATING CONDITIONS FOR EFFECTIVE LEARNING OF STUDENTS
THROUGH THE USE OF DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation. In the article, the author tries to determine effective methods of working with students in the context of the pedagogical process.

Key words: educational process, ICT technologies, students.

The Federal State Educational Standard focuses on the use of innovative teaching methods. One such solution is technical training in guardianship.

To effectively support the educational process, it is necessary to create an educational organization of a group of like-minded people - those most prepared to use DOT and owners of ICT technologies and an information educational environment (ISE).

IOS is a software and telecommunications environment that implements uniform technologies and content, high-quality information support for participants in relations training and the public.

The IOS of the gymnasium includes 3 main blocks:

- first block - organizational, pedagogical, didactic conditions for the formation and development of a rich IES;
- second block - IOS components: administrative, educational, methodological, research, extracurricular, monitoring and assessment of learning outcomes, technological support of IOS;
- third block - tools for designing and building IOS (software and hardware, organizational and methodological, communication); using the idea of a practice-oriented orientation of the educational process; software, hardware, organizational, methodological and communication tools.

Thus, an educational organization must create conditions for the functioning of an electronic information and educational environment, which includes electronic information resources, electronic educational resources, a set of information technologies, telecommunication technologies, and appropriate technological means. It is necessary to gain sufficient experience in using COR and DOT in the classroom. Today it is important to use DOT in extracurricular activities.

Tasks:

- create conditions for involving teachers in the process of producing and applying various forms of achieving educational results in extracurricular activities based on DET;
- create conditions for involving students in higher education by realizing their needs through the use of the advantages of preschool education;
- update technologies for organizing educational institutions, improving active educational practices on a remote technological basis;
- create a system for monitoring the quality of education and the effectiveness of the implementation of DET in the practice of high school education through diagnostics of the results.

Extracurricular activities (ECAs), like classroom activities, are aimed at achieving by students the planned results of mastering OEP, but first of all - at achieving personal and meta-

subject results. Today, distance learning technologies are developing very actively, and if in the recent past the teacher had only e-mail at his disposal, now special educational environments make it possible to organize an educational process that is in no way inferior in its didactic capabilities to the traditional one, and in many ways superior to it.

Distance learning is one of the forms of lifelong education, which is designed to realize the human rights to education and information.

DET is a way of organizing the educational process, based on the use of modern information and telecommunication technologies that allow learning at a distance without direct contact between teacher and student. Distance learning is an ideal aid in creating an educational space, developing students' cognitive independence and activity, and developing critical thinking.

DOT provides the opportunity to conduct remote, online Olympiads and intellectual competitions; participation in international and all-Russian educational network projects. Subject distance competitions and games are one of the forms of VUD; They contribute to the development of students' interest in the subject and expand the students' worldview.

The advantages of DOT include the following:

- accessibility,
- individualization,
- obtaining education regardless of place of residence, health status,
- creative self-expression.

The Federal State Educational Standard provides for the implementation of state policy in education, ensuring equality and accessibility of education at various starting opportunities. The requirements for the results of mastering the main educational programs, the conditions for implementation and the structure of the main educational program have changed, which are impossible without the presence of an information educational environment, the widespread use of information technologies and electronic educational resources.

Both classroom and extracurricular activities involve the introduction of new forms of work and provide for new roles: the student, as an active researcher, creatively and independently working to solve an educational problem, widely using information and communication technologies to obtain the necessary information; and the teacher as a consultant who must have the ability and skills to use computer technology. The widespread use of training using DET will help solve the problems of ensuring equal opportunities to receive high-quality general education, significantly supplement and expand the traditional forms of organizing secondary general education.

DOT becomes indispensable for children with disabilities, or those who are absent from school for a long time (under treatment, at sports camps or competitions, etc.); for students in grades 10–11 preparing to enter universities, attending preparatory courses, the schedule of which is not always coordinated with the school one.

Each student can study according to a personal schedule, varying the pace and time of study to master the material being studied. Project activities occupy a special place in extracurricular activities. It can be included in each of the areas, in any program, or can be highlighted as an independent program. Project activities are very important for further understanding the fundamentals of research activities. Distance learning also implements models of joint learning activities among students.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-3

VUD is a good opportunity for organizing interpersonal relationships in the classroom, between students and the teacher, with the aim of developing creative abilities, cognitive activity, and general cultural interests of high school students. The part-time form of VUD classes (using DOT) allows you to master part of the course via e-mail and other electronic resources.

The need to use DOT in extracurricular activities of high school students is due to various factors, among which are:

- the impossibility of constant personal presence at high school classes;
- the need for interactive interaction between students and teachers;
- work with gifted children;
- broadening one's horizons through exciting tasks (quizzes, crosswords, problems, intellectual games and game situations, virtual excursions to museums and scientific laboratories, virtual professional tests);
- display of presentations and video clips, demonstration of experiments;
- testing, laboratory and practical work;
- participation in distance competitions, competitions, projects;
- participation in online Olympiads, seminars, conferences;
- creation of creative works;
- implementation of an individual project;
- career guidance testing;
- formation of sustainable cognitive interest of students in intellectual and creative activities implemented with the help of ICT tools;
- development of the ability of free cultural communication of students with the teacher and among themselves using modern distance technologies.

In the process of conducting classes remotely, the teacher must use:

- e-mail (with its help, communication between the teacher and the student is established: sending assignments and materials; receiving notifications by the teacher about the completion of the task, individual consultations, etc.);
- Internet resources (can be used as rich illustrative or reference material for mastering VUD programs; uploading your own developments of tasks or classes).
- social networks, messengers (VKontakte, telegram).

These resources can be used as a means of communication between teachers, both with one student and with a group. Web 2.0 services: - <https://readymag.com> (creation of interactive instructions);

- <https://roundme.com> (creation of virtual panoramas);
- <https://h5p.org> (creation of an interactive dialogue simulator);
- <https://learningapps.org/> (creation of interactive content (games, puzzles, timelines, etc.)) - <http://ru.wix.com/> and [http://www.tilda.cc/ru /](http://www.tilda.cc/ru/) (creation of a Web site (page) for a teacher or student);
- Yandex Disk, RuTube
- for storing various types of files, etc.;
- Sferum
- organizing and conducting online classes. The use of DET makes it possible to improve the quality of education by increasing the share of independent mastery of the material,

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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which ensures the development of such qualities as responsibility, organization and the ability to realistically assess one's strengths and make informed decisions.

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